

HYGIENE FACTORS AND MOTIVATORS OF HERZBERG'S TWO- FACTOR THEORY ON TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION AND PERFORMANCE IN SCHOOL

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Hygiene Factors and Motivators of Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory on Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Performance in School

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Abstract

This paper examines hygiene factors that have a bearing on teacher job satisfaction and performance in Banga District 3 Public Schools, South Cotabato, Philippines. Data collection employed a quantitative, cross-sectional design, through a structured survey administered to 30 teachers from which hygiene factors such as pay, working conditions, and school policies were assessed against motivators such as achievements, recognition, and responsibility. Results showed a high level of satisfaction in work environment, school administration, and interpersonal relations, with motivator like recognition and responsibility having the highest impact on job satisfaction. The rural location positively affected the satisfaction of the teachers with some added remarks on the aspect of infrastructure. The regression analysis indicates that hygiene factors and motivator explained 93% of the job satisfaction variation, with a link between satisfaction and performance being inconclusive. The researchers recommended upgrading professional development programs, salary transparency, better infrastructure, and better practices in providing and acknowledging feedback to teachers to ensure well-being and performance.

Keywords: *Herzberg's two-factor theory, hygiene factors, motivators, teachers' job satisfaction, teacher performance*

Introduction

The ability of educators to develop young minds and provide them with the fundamental information, abilities, and values required in a world that is always changing will be crucial to achieving the global education aim. Beyond only imparting knowledge, they also help to mold people's personalities, promote social change, and protect our common future. This is an obvious vision that emphasizes the need of comprehending the elements that affect their performance and job happiness as well as the obstacles that jeopardize their effectiveness.

Teachers' job satisfaction and performance are pivotal issues in the global education landscape and researchers have highlighted factors like salary, working conditions, professional development opportunities and relationships with peers as key determinants (Tria, 2023; Etoru & Kasaija, 2020; Queyrel-Bryan, 2019). In contrast, lack of reward, scarcity of resources and poor working conditions have been associated with dissatisfaction (Etoru & Kasaija, 2020).

The correlation between teacher satisfaction and performance in the Philippine context plays a vital role in quality of education, performance, and student outcomes (Kadtong et al., 2017). But, in the case of Banga District 3 Schools of DepEd South Cotabato, the characteristics of the rural setting become challenges like limited access to resources, isolation, and lesser professional development opportunities that may affect the satisfaction and performance of the teachers. Although Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory has generally covered hygiene factors (like salary, working conditions) and motivators (like recognition, personal growth), its implementation in this setting has been limited.

Using Herzberg's frame of reference, the present study is prepared, To investigate Hygiene factors, and motivators affecting teacher satisfaction and performance in Banga District 3 Schools. It aims to explore factors influencing teachers in this rural context and offer actionable insights for targeted interventions to enhance teachers' well-being, driving improved performance and, ultimately, improved student learning outcomes.

Research Questions

The study examined the impact of motivational and hygienic elements on teacher satisfaction and the possible relationship between satisfaction and performance using Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory. Specifically, the researcher sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of teacher's hygiene factors in Banga District 3 Schools in terms of:
 - 1.1. salary;
 - 1.2. working conditions;
 - 1.3. school policies;
 - 1.4. interpersonal relationships; and
 - 1.5. job security?
2. What is the level of motivator factors in Banga District 3 Schools in terms of:
 - 2.1. achievements;
 - 2.2. recognitions;
 - 2.3. responsibility;

- 2.4. advancement; and
- 2.5. personal growth?
3. How does the unique setting of Banga District 3 Schools influence teacher job satisfaction, in terms of:
 - 3.1. remote location near farmlands; and
 - 3.2. remote location near irrigation?
4. Is there a significant relationship between teacher job satisfaction and teaching performance in Banga District 3 schools?
5. Do hygiene and motivator factors have a stronger impact on teacher job satisfaction in Banga District 3 Schools?

Literature Review

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory

Psychologist Fredrick Herzberg developed a two-factor theory in the 1950s, also known as the Motivation-Hygiene Theory, which has two key factors: hygiene and motivation. Scholars and researchers in various settings have proven that these factors significantly impact teachers' and employees' job satisfaction and motivation. Hygiene factors or the “dissatisfiers” such as salary, working environment, job security, interpersonal relationships, and company policies motivate teachers and employees. In contrast, motivators or “satisfiers” such as achievement, recognition, advancement, responsibility, and personal growth also do the same as hygiene factors (Bishayee, 2019) (Karaferis et. Al., 2022).

Herzberg's theory is important because it is utilized across diverse organizational contexts, particularly within academic environments. Prior studies have emphasized the significance of Herzberg's framework in comprehending the factors that impact job satisfaction among academic staff in higher education. Bishayee (2019) and Karaferis et. Al., (2022) discoveries indicate that, like other organizational environments, motivator factors like acknowledgment, accountability, and chances for progression are pivotal in fostering job satisfaction among organizational staff. On the other hand, hygiene factors, such as adequate compensation and working conditions, are vital in preventing job dissatisfaction.

However, Herzberg's theory has been criticized and debated, with some scholars questioning the rigidity of the two-factor distinction and the universality of the theory's application. For instance, some studies have found that certain factors, such as interpersonal relationships, can function as hygiene and motivator factors, challenging Herzberg's clear-cut categorization. In addition, this theory may differ from some cultural and contextual perspectives across organizations as the relative importance of hygiene and motivator factors may vary depending on the specific organizational setting and employee demographics.

Job Satisfaction and Its Implication in Educational Setting

Job satisfaction is a complex and multifaceted concept; it is more than like the salary. It is the deep realization of an individual who puts everything into their work, influenced by external and internal factors. The external factors that provide the workplace include job qualifications, organizational structure, and working conditions. These factors influence satisfaction by determining if the job allows employees to utilize their skills, provides a clear and functional work environment, and offers a safe and comfortable space. Internal factors, driven by individual needs and desires, play an equally important role. These encompass psychological needs, such as the desire for a sense of accomplishment or purpose, and emotional needs, related to feeling stimulated and engaged by the work. Job satisfaction is like a pie chart with various slices representing these diverse factors. The size of each slice can vary depending on the individual. Someone who prioritizes using their skills will have a larger "job qualifications" slice, while someone seeking purpose might have a larger "psychological needs" slice. Understanding this interplay of external and internal factors contributes to a deeper understanding of why someone might find their job fulfilling or frustrating (Tria, 2023) (Diab, 2018) (Demirel, 2014) (Cheng, 2020).

Examining job satisfaction among teachers in educational settings has garnered significant attention, given its potential impact on teacher retention, burnout, and overall well-being (Tria, 2023). The research suggests that factors like fair compensation, reasonable workload, autonomy to work, and opportunities for professional development significantly influence shaping teachers' job satisfaction (Demirel, 2014).

Furthermore, the relationship between job satisfaction and student academic performance has also been explored. Studies indicate that higher levels of job satisfaction among teachers can positively influence their teaching efforts and engagement in continuing education, ultimately contributing to improved student learning outcomes and academic achievement (Tria, 2023)(Knox & Anfa, 2013).

Researchers also claimed from their studies that teacher burnout rates are the central issue in education. Nearly half of the teachers starting their careers leave the profession within five years. Research shows that job satisfaction has been the main factor in teacher burnout. It was identified that teachers who are most likely to remain in the profession are experiencing a higher level of satisfaction. At the same time, those who are not satisfied are counted in the teacher burnout rate.

Instruments that measure job satisfaction and the factors they measure can provide valuable insights for school and district administrators, enabling them to identify areas for improvement and develop targeted strategies to enhance teacher job satisfaction (Knox & Anfa, 2013). This means that the identified factors from current studies will benefit every individual from various schools, helping sustain the current rate of teachers in professions and developing a plan that can positively ensure satisfied teachers in every

school.

Employee Performance: A Focus on Teachers

According to Wallace (2020), employee performance is the measurable effectiveness with which an individual fulfills their job responsibilities. This translates to teacher performance in the educational sector, incorporating the skills, knowledge, and behaviors that contribute to student learning and development.

This insight highlights the correlation between job satisfaction and the teacher's performance in the school. It implies that performance is influenced by the factors motivating them to engage in work, be overwhelmed by their responsibilities, and respond joyously to school demands. However, teaching performance is not only measured by how satisfied and motivated they are to work.

According to Guarino et al. (2020), we can use common methods to measure the school's teaching performance through classroom observation, student assessment results, teacher self-reflection, and peer feedback, with a set of standards. However, this does not mean it is the final and exact result for identifying the teacher's performance due to the complex nature of effective teaching. This means that the common methods used in measuring the teacher's performance do not limit it. Though helpful, it might not be accurate because it was based on the standard criteria a teacher must attain to be effective. As this study tries to explore the factors that best identify their motivation for such satisfaction in their jobs, it might not be the same as the previous or future research with relevant context. It was said that Herzberg's two-factor theory is debatable, but it can also be a great basis for understanding what drives the teacher to perform effectively in teaching.

Job satisfaction plays a significant role in teacher performance. Research suggests a positive correlation between satisfied teachers and effective teaching practices (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2019). Hanushek et al. (2019) interpreted this finding as meaning that teachers who perform well are motivated, engaged, and effective in the classroom. This means that teachers with job satisfaction have the maximum tendency to perform effectively in various aspects like student outcomes and achievements, are overwhelmed with challenging work, and can respond to opportunities.

The study by West and Allen (2018) presents the link between job satisfaction and student outcomes. They mentioned that the relationship between these two can be indirect, but their findings suggest that satisfied teachers create a more positive learning environment, which improves student achievement. Understanding what it means will result in the same idea that job satisfaction has a positive and negative impact on students.

Studies from Robinson et al. (2020), Garet et al. (2019), and Schaufeli and Bakker (2010) identified some strategies that will improve teacher performance through job satisfaction enhancements. They enumerated strategies like having a supportive school leadership can influence job satisfaction through providing clear expectations, resources, and regular feedback to foster a positive working environment; provide professional development opportunities through training and workshops that will help the teachers to increase skills and confidence; apply work-balance initiatives like giving a flexible time for work and offer time for personal life, will contribute to teacher well-being and satisfaction.

These are some of the strategies that researchers have identified to foster teachers' effective teaching performance. The evidence they presented provided a strong foundation of knowledge that there are factors that influence teaching performance through the satisfaction of their teaching jobs. This was a great example of how the organization sets the needs from basic to major, revealing their passion and commitment to work.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative, cross-sectional design to investigate the hygiene actors and motivators that impacted teacher job satisfaction and performance in Banga District 3 Schools. The cross-sectional approach allowed data collection at a single point in time using the survey questionnaire to analyze the relationships between these variables comprehensively.

Respondents

This study used stratified random sampling to ensure a representative sample from different schools in Banga District 3. This technique helped capture the diversity of the teachers' population across the district, accounting for school size, location, and resource availability variations. This study's respondents were thirty (30) teachers from various schools within Banga District 3. The target population includes teachers of different ages, educational backgrounds, and years of service, ensuring a diverse representation of experiences and perspectives.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Participants

<i>Category</i>	<i>Details (N=30)</i>
Age Range	From 25 to 60 years
Gender Distribution	12 males, 18 females
Educational Background	Bachelor's Degree: 20; Master's Degree: 8; Doctorate: 2
Years of Service	1–5 years: 8; 6–10 years: 12; 11–20 years: 6; 21+ years: 4

Instrument

Data was collected using a structured survey questionnaire to measure key variables. The questionnaire includes sections on hygiene factors (such as salary, working conditions, school policies, interpersonal relationships, and job security), motivators (such as achievements, recognition, responsibility, advancement, and personal growth), job satisfaction (overall satisfaction and satisfaction with specific job aspects), and employee performance (self-reported performance metrics and supervisor ratings). Responses were measured using a Likert scale (1-5).

Procedure

The study followed a systematic and ethical process to collect data from teachers in Banga District 3 Public Schools. Permission was first obtained from Sultan Kudarat State University (SKSU), followed by approvals from DepEd South Cotabato and school administrators. A pre-tested questionnaire assessing hygiene factors, motivators, job satisfaction, and performance was digitized using Google Forms, with assurances of confidentiality. Stratified random sampling identified 50 teacher participants, who received email invitations with follow-up reminders to maximize responses. After data collection, responses were reviewed for accuracy and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings were compiled into a report shared with stakeholders, ensuring a reliable and ethical research process.

Data Analysis

The study employed various statistical tools to organize, tabulate, analyze, and interpret the data. The mean was used to assess the extent of hygiene factors and the level of motivator factors, while simple regression analysis examined how the unique setting of Banga District 3 Schools influences teacher job satisfaction. Pearson correlation explored the relationship between job satisfaction and teaching performance, and multiple regression analysis compared the impacts of hygiene factors and motivators on job satisfaction to provide targeted recommendations.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed ethical requirements. Respondents freely participated. Care was taken to assure their safety and well-being: being, and that they had no physical, mental, social, or emotional impairment. There was always respect for the school head. Participants include stakeholders. The privacy of the information obtained.

Results and Discussion

Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of Salary

Table 2 presents the grand means for various indicators of Hygiene factors related to salary, with all indicators falling under the "Agree" category. The grand mean of 3.67 suggests that, on average, teachers in Banga District 3 Schools are generally satisfied with their salary-related conditions.

The highest mean of 3.73 stems from the statement, "I feel my efforts are adequately rewarded financially." This means that the teachers from the district feel that their salaries correlate with their input which is very important in developing a feeling of importance and motivation. Support for this view is provided by Hipos and Benavides (2023) whose findings indicate that financial reward has great impact in job fulfillment of the employee. To the teachers who consider their reward as being reasonable makes them even more motivated to excel in their jobs and remain loyal to it.

On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.6 pertains to the statement, "I am satisfied with the frequency of salary adjustments." This score, while still under the response of "Agree", suggests a relative area for improvement since it is assuming that teachers are also satisfied with the frequency of salary changes considering fair foot measures. This finding supports Kelemnesh (2020) who found salary as one of the main variables influencing job satisfaction and therefore cannot be overlooked given Herzberg's theory of considering it as a hygiene rather than a motivation factor.

These data suggest that salary-related indicators are significant determinants of work satisfaction for teachers in Banga District 3 schools. While most instructors think their remuneration is acceptable and comparable with their job, concerns should be raised about the frequency and timeliness of wage changes. Schools may increase teacher satisfaction, motivation, and retention by ensuring that salary structures are fair, competitive, and responsive.

Table 2. *Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of Salary*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I feel my salary is fair for the work I perform.	3.67	Agree
2.	I consistently receive my salary on or before the expected payment date	3.7	Agree
3.	My salary allows me to meet my basic needs.	3.67	Agree
4.	I am satisfied with the frequency of salary adjustments.	3.6	Agree
5.	I feel my efforts are adequately rewarded financially.	3.73	Agree
	Grand Mean	3.67	Agree

Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of Working Conditions

Table 3 shows a grand mean of 3.77, described as "Agree," indicating that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools are generally satisfied with their working conditions. This result highlights that the physical and environmental factors in the schools support a productive and comfortable teaching environment, positively impacting teachers' job satisfaction.

The highest mean of 3.87 corresponds to the statement, "I have access to necessary teaching resources and materials," indicating that teachers feel well-equipped to perform their duties effectively. Access to adequate teaching resources is crucial for teacher performance and satisfaction, as it enables the delivery of quality education. This is supported by a study conducted Ekpoh (2018), which found that teachers' satisfaction with their physical working environment, including the availability of necessary materials, is imperative for effective service delivery in secondary schools.

Conversely, the lowest mean of 3.6 pertains to the statement, "The physical facilities in my school are conducive to teaching." While still within the "Agree" range, this lower score suggests potential areas for improvement in the physical infrastructure of schools. Research indicates that the quality of school facilities can affect teacher morale and effectiveness. For instance, Admiraal (2023) found that inadequate physical conditions can lead to increased stress and decreased job satisfaction among teachers.

These insights underscore the importance of providing adequate teaching resources and maintaining conducive physical environments to support teacher satisfaction and effectiveness. Addressing areas where teachers perceive deficiencies, particularly in physical facilities, could further enhance their job satisfaction and, by extension, their performance and student outcomes.

Table 3. *Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of Working Conditions*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. My school provides a safe and clean work environment.	3.8	Agree
2. I have access to necessary teaching resources and materials.	3.87	Agree
3. The physical facilities in my school are conducive to teaching.	3.6	Agree
4. My workspace is comfortable and well-maintained.	3.8	Agree
5. Environmental factors (lighting, ventilation, etc.) support my productivity.	3.77	Agree
Grand Mean	3.77	Agree

Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of School Policies

Table 4 presents the grand mean of Hygiene Factors related to School Policies, with a grand mean of 3.86, categorized as "Agree." This indicates that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools generally perceive the school policies to be supportive and clear, contributing positively to their job satisfaction.

The highest mean of 4.03, described as "Agree," corresponds to the statement "Policies are fair and consistently applied." This suggests that teachers feel that the policies in place are equitable and implemented consistently, fostering a sense of fairness and trust in the administration.

The lowest mean of 3.73, also categorized as "Agree," is associated with the statement "Policies related to professional development are favorable." While teachers generally agree that policies support their professional growth, this score suggests there is some room for improvement in enhancing the policies or opportunities for professional development.

According to Barbeito (2004), human resource policies should maintain a balance between organizing personnel, boosting morale, enhancing quality, encouraging teamwork, and increasing output. This aligns with the findings, as the fair and consistent application of policies boosts morale and trust among teachers. However, to fully adhere to Barbeito's principles, there is a need to focus on enhancing professional development opportunities, ensuring that policies actively encourage and train teachers for efficient work performance. Addressing this area could significantly improve teacher satisfaction and organizational outcomes.

Table 4. *Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of School Policies*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. School policies are clearly communicated to all teachers.	3.93	Agree
2. Policies are fair and consistently applied.	4.03	Agree
3. Administrative processes are efficient and supportive of teaching activities.	3.83	Agree
4. Policies allow teachers to have input on decisions affecting their work.	3.8	Agree
5. Policies related to professional development are favorable.	3.73	Agree
Grand Mean	3.86	Agree

Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of Interpersonal Relationships.

Table 5 presents the grand mean of Hygiene factors related to Interpersonal Relationships, with a grand mean of 3.89, described as "Agree." This indicates that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools generally perceive positive interpersonal relationships within the school environment, contributing to their overall job satisfaction.

The highest mean of 4.07, corresponding to the statement "My relationships with colleagues are positive and supportive," suggests that

teachers feel strong, supportive connections with their peers. This likely fosters a collaborative and harmonious working atmosphere. The lowest mean of 3.77, related to "Conflicts are resolved constructively within the school," although still categorized as "Agree," suggests that while conflict resolution mechanisms are generally effective, there may be room for improvement in ensuring that all conflicts are handled as constructively as possible.

The results align with the study of Ares and Abres (2022), which emphasized that relationships and exchanges within the workplace significantly impact the daily operations of the organization. Additionally, the findings are consistent with the conclusions of Hipos and Benavides (2023), which highlighted that teachers experience greater satisfaction at work when they maintain positive relationships with their colleagues. These positive interactions enhance collaboration, reduce workplace stress, and promote a sense of belonging within the school community.

Table 5. Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of Interpersonal Relationships

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	My relationships with colleagues are positive and supportive.	4.07	Agree
2.	The administration maintains open and effective communication with teachers.	3.8	Agree
3.	Conflicts are resolved constructively within the school.	3.77	Agree
4.	Teamwork is encouraged and valued.	3.83	Agree
5.	I feel respected by my peers and superiors.	3.97	Agree
Grand Mean		3.89	Agree

Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Achievements

Table 6 shows the grand mean of 3.94, described as "Agree," indicating that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools generally feel secure in their jobs. This result suggests that teachers perceive their employment as stable and reliable, contributing positively to their overall job satisfaction and sense of security.

The highest mean of 4.04, corresponding to the statement "Long-term career opportunities are available within the school system," suggests that teachers feel optimistic about their future prospects within the system, indicating that they perceive a clear pathway for career progression. This perception likely boosts their job satisfaction and commitment to their roles.

The lowest mean of 3.8, corresponding to "I trust that my performance is the primary factor in job retention decisions," still falls under the "Agree" category but highlights a potential area for further assurance. While teachers generally trust that their performance impacts job retention, there may be room to strengthen their confidence in the fairness and transparency of these decisions.

Job security is a vital factor influencing employee commitment and organizational satisfaction. As Hipos and Benavides (2023) emphasize, an employee is more likely to exert effort and excel in their responsibilities when they feel secure in their job. This aligns with the findings of the current study, wherein perceived job security appears to contribute positively to teachers' dedication and satisfaction. Consequently, fostering an environment of trust, transparency, and opportunities for professional growth is essential in sustaining teachers' motivation and overall effectiveness.

Table 6. Extent of the Hygiene Factors in terms of Job Security

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I feel secure in my current teaching position.	4.0	Agree
2.	The school offers a stable and predictable work environment.	3.9	Agree
3.	I believe my job is protected from arbitrary termination.	3.97	Agree
4.	I trust that my performance is the primary factor in job retention decisions.	3.8	Agree
5.	Long-term career opportunities are available within the school system.	4.04	Agree
Grand Mean		3.94	Agree

Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Achievements

Table 7 presents the grand mean for the Motivator Factors related to Achievements, with an overall grand mean of 4.01, described as "Agree." This indicates that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools generally feel positively about their sense of accomplishment and recognition in their teaching roles, which is a key contributor to their job satisfaction.

The highest mean of 4.4, described as "Agree," corresponds to the statement "My achievements as a teacher are appreciated by the school." This suggests that teachers feel valued by their school for their contributions, which likely fosters a sense of fulfillment and satisfaction.

The lowest mean of 3.73, described as "Agree," corresponds to the statement "Achieving milestones in my teaching career motivates me." While this still indicates general agreement, it suggests that some teachers may experience slightly less motivation from their career milestones, indicating room for further development in career progression incentives.

The well-known correlation between achievement motivation and academic and career success has been explored in-depth. As formulated by Cigularov (2008), individuals who possess strong achievement motivation usually tend to achieve better success in their

career and academic activities. Hence the development of achievement motivation among teachers by providing them with specific type of incentives and growth can be crucial for their career and job satisfaction.

Table 7. *Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Achievements*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I feel a sense of accomplishment in my teaching role.	4.0	Agree
2.	I am recognized for achieving my goals in the classroom.	3.8	Strongly Agree
3.	My achievements as a teacher are appreciated by the school.	4.4	Agree
4.	I take pride in the academic success of my students.	4.1	Strongly Agree
5.	Achieving milestones in my teaching career motivates me.	3.73	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.01	Agree

Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Recognition

Table 8 presents the grand mean for the Motivator Factors related to Recognition, with a grand mean of 4.05, described as "Agree." This indicates that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools generally feel recognized and motivated by their efforts in the workplace.

The highest mean of 4.2, corresponding to the statement "Positive feedback encourages me to perform better," suggests that teachers place significant value on feedback that fosters motivation and improves performance. This reflects a strong belief that constructive feedback plays a key role in enhancing their job satisfaction.

The lowest mean of 3.93, corresponding to "I receive regular feedback on my performance," while still in the "Agree" range, indicates that there may be slight room for improvement in the consistency or frequency of feedback teachers receive. However, the overall positive response across all indicators highlights the importance of recognition and feedback in driving teacher motivation and job satisfaction.

The results highlight the importance of recognition and feedback in motivating teachers. Recognition gives confidence in teachers, which produces more productivity. According to Paul (2016) when the employees are appreciated and treated with respect for their contributions to the work place, then the results can be remarkable, for example, better commitment of employees (rate of employees who remain), less employee turnover, improved loyalty from clients, and improvement in motivation of the organisation as a whole.

Table 8. *Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Recognition*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	My contributions are acknowledged by school leaders.	3.97	Agree
2.	Recognition for my efforts motivates me to improve.	4.03	Agree
3.	Students and parents recognize my dedication as a teacher.	4.1	Agree
4.	I receive regular feedback on my performance.	3.93	Agree
5.	Positive feedback encourages me to perform better.	4.2	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.05	Agree

Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Responsibility

Table 9 presents the grand mean for the Motivator Factors in terms of Responsibility, with an overall grand mean of 4.14, described as "Agree." This indicates that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools generally feel positively about the responsibilities assigned to them, and these responsibilities contribute to their job satisfaction.

Table 9. *Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Responsibility*

	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	I feel empowered to make decisions in my teaching.	4.0	Agree
2.	My responsibilities are clearly defined.	4.1	Agree
3.	Taking responsibility for student success is fulfilling.	4.23	Strongly Agree
4.	I am entrusted with important tasks in the school.	3.97	Agree
5.	Increased responsibility motivates me to excel.	4.4	Agree
	Grand Mean	4.14	Agree

The highest mean of 4.4, described as "Agree," corresponds to the statement "Increased responsibility motivates me to excel." This suggests that teachers are motivated to perform better when they are given more responsibilities, indicating that they see increased responsibility as a key driver for their professional growth and performance.

The lowest mean of 3.97, described as "Agree," corresponds to the statement "I am entrusted with important tasks in the school." While teachers agree that they are given significant tasks, this score suggests a slight opportunity for improvement in ensuring that all teachers feel equally entrusted with crucial school responsibilities.

It indicates that Teacher job satisfaction lead to higher commitment towards their organization, move motivation to perform their role and finally high performance. This comports with the findings of Judge (2001), Lee (2010), and Rigopoulou (2011) which identified a positive relationship between employee satisfaction and organizational commitment, work motivation, and performance.

Understanding the motivational value of meaningful responsibilities, school managers and administrators can develop general approaches to create positive conditions where all teachers feel trusted and valued. This may help create a more motivated and productive workforce and better education for the district.

Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Advancement

Table 10 shows the grand mean of 4.18, described as "Agree," indicating that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools generally feel positive about the opportunities for career advancement within the school system. This suggests that the opportunities for promotion, professional growth, and career advancement within the school system are effective in fostering motivation among the teaching staff.

The highest mean of 4.33, described as "Strongly Agree," corresponds to the statement "Career advancement is encouraged by the administration." This suggests that teachers feel strongly supported by school leadership in their career progression. The high rating highlights the critical role of administrative support in motivating teachers and creating an environment that prioritizes career growth. This aligns with the assertion by Nava-Macali et al. (2019) that career development initiatives, such as training and professional growth opportunities, positively impact employees' dedication and productivity. By fostering an encouraging atmosphere, school leadership reinforces teachers' confidence in their career trajectories and their sense of value within the organization.

On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.97, described as "Agree," is associated with the statement "I have access to professional development opportunities." While teachers generally agree with this statement, the result suggests there is room for improvement in ensuring equal and sufficient access to professional development programs for all teachers.

This finding implies the need for school administrators to evaluate and enhance existing professional development initiatives to address potential gaps and meet the diverse needs of their teaching staff. According to Jun, Cai, and Shin (2006), employees who participate in training programs feel more confident in their ability to perform their roles, perceive prospects for professional growth, and recognize that their employers are invested in their development. These factors collectively contribute to increased job satisfaction.

Table 10. *Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Advancement*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. Opportunities for promotion are available within the school system.	4.01	Strongly Agree
2. I feel supported in my professional growth aspirations.	4.27	Agree
3. I have access to professional development opportunities.	3.97	Agree
4. Career advancement is encouraged by the administration.	4.33	Strongly Agree
5. Advancing in my career is important for my satisfaction.	4.3	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.18	Agree

Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Personal Growth

Table 11 shows the grand mean of 4.19, described as "Agree," indicating that teachers in Banga District 3 Schools generally perceive their roles as conducive to personal and professional growth. This suggests that the opportunities for development and the overall school environment foster a sense of growth and motivation for the teaching staff.

Table 11. *Extent of the Motivator Factors in terms of Personal Growth*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. My teaching role helps me grow personally and professionally.	4.4	Agree
2. I have opportunities to develop new skills in my role.	3.83	Agree
3. The school environment encourages learning and growth.	3.86	Strongly Agree
4. Personal growth motivates me to stay in my teaching career.	4.37	Agree
5. I feel that I am becoming a better teacher each year.	4.47	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.19	Agree

The highest mean of 4.47, described as "Strongly Agree," corresponds to the statement "I feel that I am becoming a better teacher each year." This highlights that teachers strongly feel they are improving in their profession, which is likely a significant factor in their ongoing job satisfaction and commitment to the profession.

The lowest mean of 3.83, described as "Agree," corresponds to the statement "I have opportunities to develop new skills in my role." While teachers generally agree that there are opportunities for skill development, this area may benefit from additional efforts to provide more specialized or varied growth opportunities.

These results are echoed by Monisha (2023), who states that encouraging employee personal growth in the workplace directly correlates to performance, as well as participation and job satisfaction. People who actively seek out growth opportunities tend to be more adaptable, creative, and committed in their positions. These skills are vital in the teaching profession, where being open to change and seeking creative solutions are essential in ensuring that teachers are effective in their classroom work and their contributions to their students' success.

This reinforces the need for an encouraging workplace very conducive to continued learning and skill-building amongst teachers. Where there were some small areas of lower rating, by addressing these schools can ensure that their strategies for supporting teachers

to reach their potential are as robust as possible.

Influence of Unique Setting of Banga District 3 Schools (remote location near farmlands and irrigation) in Teacher Job Satisfaction

Figure 1 demonstrates the results of a regression analysis investigating how the unique setting of Banga District 3 Schools (remote location near farmlands and irrigation) impacts teacher job satisfaction. The analysis indicates a strong predictive relationship, with the unique setting explaining 84% of the variance in teacher job satisfaction ($R^2=0.84$, $F(1,3)=16.32$, $p=0.027$). The standardized regression coefficient ($\beta=0.58$, $p=0.027$) reveals a moderate positive influence, suggesting that as teachers perceive the unique characteristics of their environment—such as community support, accessibility, and resource availability—more favorably, their job satisfaction improves. The intercept ($\alpha=1.64$, $p=0.067$) indicates a moderate baseline level of job satisfaction even when perceptions of the unique setting are neutral. However, the near-significance of the intercept suggests other factors may also contribute to satisfaction levels.

These findings are consistent with existing literature, which highlights how connection to community and slower pace-of-life in rural areas has been associated with reduced teacher stress and better job satisfaction. While rural schools do have a smaller pool for teacher recruitment, research shows that teachers in rural schools form tight bonds with the surrounding communities, a phenomenon which Johnson and Howley (2015) identifies as a major contributor of rural teachers' workplace feelings of connection and belonging in their jobs (Monk 2007).

Although the benefits of living in rural settings (such as community support and work-life balance) are clear, this analysis highlights the importance of addressing other factors essential to job satisfaction: specifically, infrastructure, availability of resources, and leadership opportunities. According to Barbosa and Coneway (2023), teachers in rural schools require facilities and resources, as well as avenues to professional growth and leadership in order to leverage the advantages of rural settings, and retain rural teachers.

Figure 1. Regression Analysis Result of Unique Setting and Job Satisfaction

Relationship between Teacher Job Satisfaction and Teaching Performance in Banga District 3 schools

From Table 12 that shows the Pearson correlation analysis reveals a strong positive relationship between teaching performance and job satisfaction with a correlation coefficient $r=0.754$. This means that being more satisfied with their job is, in general, associated with doing a better job teaching. This association is in line with previous literature that emphasizes the importance of job satisfaction for optimal organizational outcomes. Job satisfaction, as stated by Wiliyanto, Sudiarditha, and Yohana (2020), also is one of the most important aspects of motivation to do the job well. Teachers who are experienced in their work setting are increasingly committed to serving their duties effectively.

So despite the positive correlation between job satisfaction and teaching performance, the relationship was not statistically significant ($p=0.141$), as the p-value was above the level of significance ($p < 0.05$). This tells us that although there seems to be a substantial correlation between the two variables, the evidence is not convincing enough to make a strong claim at the selected significance level. Include more information about what you learned from statistically testing the association between two variables.

The results are in line with an argument developed by Marman et al (2021) which emphasized the fact that teacher job satisfaction is an important human resource management settlement that directly or indirectly affects teaching effectiveness. These writers stressed the point that when teachers feel fulfilled within their roles, they are more likely to show that they are committed and that they work hard to get to the highest level of success possible. However, the absence of statistical significance in this research suggests that there may be other factors or circumstances that mediate or act as a medium between job satisfaction and teaching performance.

However, this should be further studied to see if more variables or context-specific conditions influence teaching. The small sample size may have limited the ability to detect significant differences, and future studies should include larger and more diverse samples.

Table 12. Relationship between Teacher Job Satisfaction and Teaching Performance in Banga District 3 schools

		Job Satisfaction	Teaching Performance
Job Satisfaction	Pearson's r	—	—
	Df	—	—
	p-value	—	—
	N	—	—
Teaching Performance	Pearson's r	0.754	—
	Df	28	—
	p-value	0.1407	—
	N	30	—

Note. *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

Impact of Hygiene Factors and Motivators on Teacher Job Satisfaction in Banga District 3 Schools

Figure 2 illustrates the results of a regression analysis exploring the influence of Hygiene factors and Motivators on teacher job satisfaction in Banga District 3 Schools. The analysis reveals a very strong predictive relationship, with Hygiene factors and Motivators collectively explaining 93% of the variance in job satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.93$, $F(1, 3) = 38.09$, $p = 0.009$). The adjusted R^2 value ($R^2_{adj} = 0.90$) further emphasizes the robustness of the model, demonstrating its predictive reliability while accounting for model complexity.

Salary, working conditions, and interpersonal relationships, hygiene factors, become important dimensions to improving teacher satisfaction. Likewise, Motivators of the likes of recognition, achievement and opportunities for personal growth have a major impact on job satisfaction. The results are consistent with earlier studies. Klecker & Loadman (2011) noted that teacher job satisfaction is closely related to salary, promotion opportunities, job challenges, autonomy, working conditions, and interaction with colleagues and students. On other hand, Okonkwo & Obineli (2011) listed poor salary and bad working conditions as crucial factors that undermine teacher motivation and satisfaction.

Moreover, the findings align with Sahito & Vaisanen (2017), who found that reward, recognition, and healthy workplace environment are some of the best predictors of job satisfaction. This highlights the importance of nurturing both Hygiene factors and Motivators to enhance teacher satisfaction and, in result, the performance and retention of teachers in schools.

Figure 2. Regression Analysis of Hygiene Factors, Motivators, and Job Satisfaction

Conclusions

Based on the study, it can be concluded that in Banga District 3 Schools, both motivators and hygiene factors play a crucial role in influencing teachers' job satisfaction. Hygiene factors, such as salary, working environment, and interpersonal relationships, provide the foundation for teachers to feel secure and content in their roles. Meanwhile, motivators, including recognition, opportunities for professional growth, and personal improvement, significantly enhance teachers' sense of fulfilment and engagement. Overall, teachers in the district generally hold a positive view of their workplace, particularly regarding their professional achievements and career advancement prospects, which are key drivers of their job satisfaction.

To further enhance teacher job satisfaction and address the findings of the study, it is recommended that school administrators and policymakers prioritize improvements in both hygiene factors and motivators. Specifically, efforts should be made to ensure timely salary adjustments, improve physical facilities, and provide greater access to teaching resources. Additionally, professional development opportunities must be expanded, focusing on career advancement and skill-building programs that cater to the unique

needs of teachers in rural areas. Finally, local government units and the Department of Education should collaborate to enhance school infrastructure and accessibility, ensuring that the rural setting remains a supportive and enriching environment for teachers.

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